

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ В ВЫПОЛНЕНИИ ЗАДАЧ, ПОСТАВЛЕННЫХ ПЕРЕД УЧАЩИМИСЯ ЧЛЕНАМИ КОМАНДЫ.

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Аннотация: в этой статье рассказывается о социальной деятельности преподавателей и их особой важности для коллектива студентов, об образовательном процессе, который проводится с коллективом студентов, чтобы показать студентам, что общение имеет ценное значение в процессе коллективной деятельности.

Ключевые слова: педагог, профессиональная деятельность, читатель, цель, самоуправление.

In the process of teamwork, educators are required to make extensive use of research and teaching methods for independent research. Students cognitive activity, thinking, worldview, and ability to master social norms expand.

Circumstances aimed at solving the problem and the optimal ways to solve this problem play a key role in the technology of exploratory training. The main purpose of organizing such classes is to create a favorable pedagogical environment for members of the student body to seek answers to all questions. As a result of this relationship, students learn to learn independently, make decisions, and respect the opinions of others.

The process of working with a team of students is based on the following principles:

- the right of the teacher and all students to creative activity on the basis of equality;
- creating opportunities for team members to evaluate themselves and each other;
- creation of favorable pedagogical conditions for mutual exchange of individual and collective work, creating an environment of mutual understanding, cooperation, development of communicative culture;
- the need to use the method of error correction and testing, as well as research and development methods;
- the creation of a problem-solving situation for members of the student community;
- Opportunity to engage in dialogue in all classes;

- Problem-solving and inquisitive situations created by teachers can serve to ensure activity and independence of students;
- the creation of favorable conditions for the practical activities of members of the student body in the educational process.

In the process of working with a team of students, all the technologies used by teachers should be algorithmic:

1. Orientation of educational technology to the content of student activities. This creates problematic, exploratory learning situations. The professionalism of the educator plays an important role in creating such a situation.

2. Organization of specially designed learning situations. At the same time, students work independently on the learning materials provided to students. In the process of finding solutions to tasks, team members enter into situations of mutual cooperation, debate. In the process of completing the given task, the teacher gives the necessary advice to the students and takes the position of facilitator.

3. Social constructions. In this case, the members of the class team are divided into several groups. They think about solutions to a particular task and work together to accomplish it.

4. Technologies of socialization of students. During independent learning, they develop as a result of students interacting with each other. Team members encourage each student to act creatively. As a member of the group, explaining the solution to this or that situation creates a favorable environment for the student to demonstrate their abilities in the team.

5. Information Request Situation. This situation arises as a result of the ability of the team members of the students to demonstrate the product of the joint activity.

6. The situation of self-expression in the team. In this process, an atmosphere of discussion is created, with each student expressing his or her views on the issue to the team members. In this way, supporters and denials of his opinion emerge. The student is able to express himself while substantiating his opinion.

All members of the class team should be able to analyze, diagnose, and evaluate their own activities and behaviors at each stage of the session. Based on this analysis, the student team and the teacher work together to improve the next stages of the learning process.

The effectiveness of teamwork can be seen in the fact that in the process, students' interest in learning and competition increases. They will have the

opportunity to act independently, to trust each other, to encourage each other to succeed.

The distinctive features of the student community are the integration of peer-to-peer, spiritually close subjects, the ability to carry out educational work in accordance with the age characteristics, the ease of creating an environment of cooperation in the classroom.

To work effectively with a team of students, educators must meet the following requirements:

- be able to establish friendly relations with team members;
- focus on the mental, spiritual, physical development and health of team members;
- be able to create a cultural, informative, student-centered learning environment in the classroom;
- be able to take into account the gender characteristics of the student body, etc.

In the process of teamwork, students should develop the following skills:

- be able to take a critical approach to the activities of himself and his classmates;
- compare and objectively evaluate the results of their academic work with their classmates;
- be able to work together for the success of the team;
- be able to jointly overcome obstacles in the process of teamwork;
- learning to communicate and cooperate with others.

In order to effectively organize the process of working with a team of students, educators must follow the following rules:

1. To diagnose the level of productivity of pedagogical tools, methods and techniques used in the process of working with a group of students.
2. Selection and systematization of tasks to be presented with distinctive features of each member of the student team, gender characteristics.
3. Develop the ability of members of the student community to objectively evaluate the results of their joint activities.
4. In the process of educational activities, teachers should pay attention to the planning of educational activities aimed at developing the cultural, spiritual and moral skills of the student body.
5. Identify the mistakes made by each member of the student team, both himself and his teammates, and achieve a clear assessment of himself and each other's achievements.
6. It is advisable to set clear requirements for members of the student body and to objectively assess their compliance with these requirements.

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